

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

FAIR Assessment: SSHOC-CESSDA Conceptual Requirements

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0.4	Draft	2025-12-12	Added boilerplate	John Shepherdson
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1.0	Issue	2026-01-06	Added links to Benchmark and Specialised Metric definitions in FAIRsharing. Moved metrics relating to use of CESSDA and DDI Controlled Vocabularies from R2 to I1.3	John Shepherdson

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Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
CV	Controlled Vocabulary
GUPRI	Globally unique, persistent and resolvable
GUID	Globally unique and resolvable. Note that often people use this (mistakenly) interchangeably with GUPRI.

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Introduction and Task Management

This document describes a FAIR benchmark and its associated components, tailored to the needs of the CESSDA community. This document is a human-readable, narrative description of this community's requirements for FAIR assessment of the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) - descriptive DDI metadata of datasets - within social sciences, without the inclusion of technical details. It follows the [Assess-IF](#) and, once complete, can be used as a starting point for the creation of required technical components.

The following arguments should be passed to this benchmark:

- Mandatory: The GUPRI (or another identifier such as URL) for the digital object being assessed.
- Optional: The FAIRsharing URL or DOI for the database that stores the digital object being assessed. While not required, passing this argument will allow more information about the digital object and its holding database to be retrieved.

This document was created using a template found at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17901311>. This template can be copied and used within any community to begin preparations for a FAIR benchmark specific to your needs.

The tables below should be used to keep track of your progress and provide attribution.

FAIR Assessment Conceptual Components - Roadmap		
Task	Status	Notes
1: Benchmark – narrative requirements	Done	Mark as complete when Benchmark section in this document is completed. Iterative refinement may be required before completing step 4.
2: All metrics - narrative requirements	Done	Mark as complete when all metric sections in this document are completed. Iterative refinement may be required before completing step 4.
3: Related standards, databases and collections - registration with FAIRsharing	Done	Any standards, databases and collections that are required for the correct running of your benchmark should be registered with FAIRsharing and listed in the ‘Related Records’ area of the metrics sections.

4: Completed first draft of document	Done	Once all parties are happy with this document, the first draft is complete, and the next task may begin.
5: Benchmark - registration with FAIRsharing	Done	FAIR Benchmark - CESSDA Data Catalogue: https://fairsharing.org/7609
6: All metrics - registration with FAIRsharing	Done	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses CESSDA Topic Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7576</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Analysis Unit Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7575</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Contains CESSDA Provenance Information: https://fairsharing.org/7571</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Time Method Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7573</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Mode Of Collection Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7574</p> <p>FAIR Metric– F1-PID – Metadata - Identifiers use ARK, DOI, HANDLE or URN PID schemas: https://fairsharing.org/7564</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Sampling Procedure Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7572</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses CESSDA ELSST Keywords: https://fairsharing.org/7577</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata uses CESSDA Access Rights Vocabulary: https://fairsharing.org/7578</p> <p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Conforms to CESSDA DDI Codebook Profile - https://fairsharing.org/7610</p>

Overview

The Assessment Interoperability Framework (Assess-IF) being used by this community aims to create a uniform approach for defining and running tests (and specifically FAIR tests in the context of this document) by:

1. **Giving the community the power to choose what FAIR means to them:** Until now, using a FAIR tool such as those listed at <https://fairassist.org/tools> meant either selecting from among the benchmarks for FAIR that a given tool provides (which may be unclear or hard to understand exactly what's being tested) or a formal collaboration with tool(s) to ensure they provide a custom FAIR assessment solution for your needs. The Assess-IF allows you to explicitly state how your community defines FAIR, and exactly how it should be tested, measured, weighted and scored.
2. **Encouraging transparency in assessment behaviours:** To date, FAIR assessment has been characterised by disparate behaviours and scores arising from independently authored FAIR Assessment tools, which themselves vary in the level of transparency they exhibit for their tests and benchmarks. The Assess-IF methodology encourages all tools and assessment platforms to register their assessment components (e.g. benchmarks, metrics) in a searchable manner, with rich metadata explaining what is being tested, why, and how. The Assess-IF allows you not only to define FAIR according to your community requirements but also provides a way of making those definitions clear, visible, reusable and extendable. Benchmarks that cannot be discovered via a search, and do not describe themselves sufficiently, do not themselves meet the minimum expectations for FAIRness and make it harder to understand if a particular tool interprets FAIR the way your community requires it to be interpreted.
3. **Defining a consistent report format for assessments:** Because the reports are designed to be understood by any tool, the user can have a wider range of independent tools to select from. Being able to move these reports from one tool to another also allows the user to contextualise their tests, and to explore results from different perspectives.
4. **Enabling Automatic FAIR Testing via APIs:** by creating shared APIs among the different domains (FAIR, SKG, DMP, maDMP) it becomes possible to “embed” assessments into existing tooling. For example, a DMP authoring tool will be able to “call out” to a FAIR Assessment tool to obtain real-time information about the FAIRness of a digital object while the DMP is being written or updated.

Summary of component types

The Assess-IF has seven main “components”, split according to three main categories: **conceptual** components define FAIR for a community in human-readable terms, **software** components provide the actual tests and interpretations of those tests, and **data** components store the results of running an assessment. This template helps you to fully specify the conceptual components for your community definition of FAIR and gives you jumping off points to create the software components and ultimately run assessments to produce data in the form of test results. As such, we have provided a short description of each component so that you can understand the wider framework at a very high level.

The **conceptual components** are:

1. **Dimensions/principles:** Dimensions (for this template, our dimensions are the FAIR Principles) are designed to be subject- and implementation-agnostic criteria or high-level goals that may be refined for particular communities as described in this template. More information on the FAIR principles can be found in the FAIR Principles FAIRsharing record (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.WWI10U>), which provides a wealth of information about them as well as linking to individual records describing all sub-principles.
2. **Benchmarks:** Community-specific groupings of metrics. They provide a narrative describing how a community defines FAIR. Communities can choose the granularity of their benchmarks with regards to subject area and digital object type. Specifically, this means that benchmarks may be agnostic of object type or subject area, or may be scoped as tightly as required by the benchmark authors.
3. **Metrics:** Narrative description that a Test must wholly implement. Each metric should implement exactly one dimension (e.g. one sub-principle from the FAIR Principles). Metrics may be domain-agnostic or not.

A detailed understanding of the remaining components (below) is not required for the purposes of this template, but a short description of each is provided for completeness.

The **software components** are:

1. **Tests:** The instantiation of metrics, executed to assess a digital object in accordance with the metric linked to the test.

2. **Scoring Algorithms:** The instantiation of benchmarks, executed to create community-specific value judgements on the outcomes of tests. They specify the exact set of tests which are to be run by the assessment service together with weightings for each of these tests. Algorithms contextualise the sum of all test results for a given benchmark into a final quantitative assessment result.

The **data components** are:

1. **Test Results:** The output of running a test over a digital object. A test result also contains provenance metadata about the process followed to create it.
2. **Test Result Sets:** A set of test results, together with their respective metadata.
3. **Benchmark Scores:** Obtained after executing a scoring algorithm over a set of test results. The benchmark score includes a value, a log and a link to the test results used to obtain the score.

Understanding and using this template

This template is organised into multiple sections to help you define your conceptual components and begin to think about your software components. It is deliberately written without exposing too much of the underlying framework, to simplify the task of creating your specific FAIR requirements. When complete, you will not only have defined your Assess-IF conceptual components, but you will also be ready to begin the iterative development of the software components.

There is one benchmark section followed by metric sections named according to the FAIR principle they implement. If you have more than one metric for any principle, please add sub-headings within its section.

Types of Metrics

Symbols

indicate a Generic metric.

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💡 indicates a Specialised metric.

📖 indicates a section providing more information.

When a community uses this document to describe a benchmark and related metrics, the metrics can be one of two types.

Within OStrails, all principles have corresponding **generic metrics** except for the following: I2, R1.2, R1.3, which communities must **specialise** for their requirements. Such specialised metrics generally need to consider the requirements of both the specific discipline and digital object type being assessed by the benchmark.

Generic Metrics

✅ If a section is labelled **generic**, then all benchmarks should be able to implement the generic metric rather than needing to define a community-specific metric. Generic metrics are those that cover domain-agnostic features, therefore applicable to any discipline, irrespective of the type of digital object being evaluated.

Specialised Metrics

💡 If a section is labelled **specialised**, then the principle is considered highly domain specific, and we suggest that all communities create their own metric to suit their requirements.

Refinements and sufficiency

Small modifications to existing generic metrics may optionally be added as **refinements** to a generic metric within a community document. These are intended to allow communities to specify exactly where a field can be found, e.g. a licence field, within their metadata. These will either be implemented as a specialised test (rather than using the already-created generic test associated with a generic metric) or as a specialised metric. Iterative updates to this document will determine which is appropriate.

While the classification of **generic** and **specialised** metrics is useful and is intended to make it easier to create assessments, there will be circumstances where a given **generic** metric is a *necessary* part of the assessment for a community but is also *insufficient* to wholly describe that community’s requirements for that principle.

For example, perhaps a community wishes to specifically check for a particular type of DOI (e.g. one minted by an approved service of their choice) in addition to the presence of any GUPRI type (“any GUPRI” is the definition of the generic F1 GUID metric). In such a case, **refinements** are not appropriate (because the underlying generic metric is *necessary* but not *sufficient*); instead, **specialised** metrics linked to a principle that already has a **generic** metric are appropriate. In this example, the community should use two metrics, both of which are linked to FAIR F1-GUID: one will be the **generic** metric for FAIR F1-GUID and the other will be a new **specialised** metric with the added requirement.

Benchmark

Benchmark Name	<i>CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) Benchmark</i>
Description	FAIR Benchmark - CESSDA Data Catalogue (FB-CDC) is intended to ensure that metadata records it contains are FAIR. It is of primary utility for data curators, repository managers, metadata quality assessors, and data infrastructure maintainers working with social science research data. This benchmark coordinates the FAIR assessment of CDC metadata records using a mixture of generic and specialised metrics.
Applicability	<i>What <u>digital object(s)</u> will be covered? CESSDA Data Catalogue study level metadata records.</i> <i>What <u>subject area(s)</u> are covered by this benchmark? Social science research outputs contained in the CESSDA Data Catalogue.</i>
Related Resources	This benchmark relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7609
Guidance	More information on this benchmark may be found at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESSDA Vocabulary Service https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/ • CESSDA ELSST https://thesauri.cessda.eu/elsst-6/en/ • CDC DDI Profiles https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html

- DANS FAIR Assessment Guidance <https://fairassessment.dansdemo.nl/guidance>

FAIR Principles F1: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

F1 states that (Meta)data should be assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers that serve as a permanent, machine interpretable reference. As such, this principle also relates to resolvability of the identifiers within FAIR Principle A1. Globally unique means that the identifier is guaranteed to unambiguously refer to the intended resources, making locally uniqueness (e.g. unique within a single, local database) insufficient. Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused in another context, and continues to identify the same resource over time, even if that resource should no longer exist, or moves from one digital environment to another. While global uniqueness is a technical property (i.e., an algorithm that can guarantee with mathematical precision that the issued identifiers are unique), persistence is a social commitment made by the stakeholder responsible for issuing the identifiers, that these identifiers will continue to map to the objects they identify for a defined period of time. Due to the relationship among global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability, please note that the GO FAIR Foundation states that FAIR implementations should have Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs). (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed in <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a2cea7>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a2cea7>.

 The metrics relating to this principle are **generic** and are implemented via its sub-principles (see the next two sections).

This principle is very commonly split into its distinct components of the identifiers being checked for 1) persistence, and 2) global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability. As such, the **generic metrics** in use for F1 are also split between sub-principles F1-PID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>) and F1-GUID (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>).

Use the next two card sets to either state your community's alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition for F1-PID and F1-GUID.

FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers

'FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers' further refines the F1 principle that covers both global uniqueness and persistence to consider only the persistence aspects. Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused in another context, and continues to identify the same resource over time, even if that resource should no longer exist, or moves from one digital environment to another. Persistence is a social commitment made by the stakeholder responsible for issuing the identifiers, that these identifiers will continue to map to the objects they identify for a defined period of time. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed in <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**. This is the first of two sub-principles of F1.

FAIR Principles F1-PID: (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Persistence - Gen2-MI-F1B</p> <p><i>This metric checks whether the identifier schema the provided identifier adheres to is persistent. Gen2-MI-F1B is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier to be provided and evaluates its identifier schema for persistence. An example implementation would be to use regex matching against registered FAIRsharing identifier schemata and check the persistence field (see support links in this record for more information). More than one match might signify an issue with the identifier schema matching. If using this example implementation, check the existing identifier schemata in FAIRsharing and please register any that you might need. Although persistence is an important attribute of identifiers, it should be assessed in conjunction with global uniqueness and resolvability. This is because the choice of identifier scheme will have widespread implications for resource lookup, linking, and data sharing.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>🔗 For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.VRo9DI.</p> <p>🔗 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e226cb.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p><i>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</i></p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

Differences from the Generic Metric

This section should be removed from your document if you are using the generic metric without modification, or if this principle and associated metric are not applicable to your community.

Description of differences from the generic metric	<p>FAIR Metric – F1-PID – Metadata - Identifiers use ARK, DOI, HANDLE or URN PID schemas is a metadata metric that requires the minting of persistent identifiers for at least some of the content within the metadata record being evaluated. FM_F1-PID_M_CESSDA expects a metadata identifier as its input and evaluates the metadata record for the presence of an implemented id schema (CESSDA requires the use of ARK, DOI, HANDLE or URN PID schemas. Other schemas are considered invalid). As described by the GO FAIR Foundation, global uniqueness guarantees the unambiguous referencing of the described resource; it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally. Persistence refers to the requirement that this globally unique identifier is never reused elsewhere and continues to identify the same resource over time. These features are key to the Findability of the metadata record being evaluated.</p>					
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAIR F1-PID - (Meta)data are assigned persistent identifiers • Archival Resource Key (ARK) • Digital Object Identifier (DOI) • Handle (hdl) • Uniform Resource Name (URN) • https://fairsharing.org/7564 					
Guidance	<p>Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="253 1034 2143 1273"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="253 1034 1462 1114">URI</th> <th data-bbox="1473 1034 2143 1114">Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="253 1114 1462 1273"> https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs </td> <td data-bbox="1473 1114 2143 1273"> <p>CESSDA Persistent Identifier Types vocabulary: JSON API documentation for retrieving approved PID schemas and understanding vocabulary structure</p> </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs	<p>CESSDA Persistent Identifier Types vocabulary: JSON API documentation for retrieving approved PID schemas and understanding vocabulary structure</p>
URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI					
https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs	<p>CESSDA Persistent Identifier Types vocabulary: JSON API documentation for retrieving approved PID schemas and understanding vocabulary structure</p>					

	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/CessdaPersistentIdentifierTypes?lang=en		CESSDA Persistent Identifier Types vocabulary: Information how to use vocabulary
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/anlyUnit.html		DDI 2.5 IDNo specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>IDNo</i> element and its attribute <i>agency</i> in DDI metadata
	https://cmv.CESSDA.eu/documentation/profiles.html		CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>IDNo</i> element and its <i>agency</i> attribute in CESSDA
	https://zenodo.org/records/3611324		CESSDA ERIC Persistent Identifier Policy Best Practice Guidelines: Guidelines for the implementation of the CESSDA Persistent Identifier Policy Principles
	https://www.westminster.ac.uk/research/researcher-support/open-access/what-are-persistent-identifiers		FAIR principles and persistent identifiers: General information about the role of PIDs in achieving Findability and Accessibility in research data management
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=77dadf37f4bf042e1c7fa96505219e21d588305cb9b10ca7c67f2d8e5928c46c	DDI <i>IDNo</i> element with <i>agency</i> ="DOI"

	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=4c70d55197e2c80afe593f8463e4edc4ee441e70c356a64dba20208758291394	DDI <i>IDNo</i> element with <i>agency="Handle"</i>
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=d9645fff23e974fcb3bca529d9b47033c1a43672ec827c0591ea351ed8323b47	DDI <i>IDNo</i> element with <i>agency="URN"</i>
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=f0f123047653a7ea42143642110202f3e6822da5d4867aefbf7333937ec6b15f	<i>IDNo</i> elements present but <i>agency</i> attribute uses schema which is not approved by this metric
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=795d5e7a3060962626c3b8ffa8826865360edfc898ed65ed58a10f49a19cd59	<i>IDNo</i> elements present but missing <i>agency</i> attribute
	Indeterminate	Any CESSD catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

'FAIR Principles F1-GUID: (Meta)data are assigned globally unique identifiers' further refines the F1 principle that covers both global uniqueness and persistence to consider only the global uniqueness aspects. Globally unique means that the identifier is guaranteed to unambiguously refer to the intended resources (where 'global' is intended to mean 'universal' as there are described digital assets outside the 'world'). Therefore, it is insufficient for it to be unique only locally (e.g. unique within a single, local database). Global uniqueness is a technical property (i.e., an algorithm that can guarantee with mathematical precision that the issued identifiers are unique). (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed in <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**. This is the second of two sub-principles of F1.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness - Gen2-MI-F1A</p> <p><i>The 'FAIR Maturity Indicator - Identifier Uniqueness' metric checks whether the identifier schema the provided identifier adheres to is globally unique, persistent and resolvable (a GUPRI); a pass of tests implementing both this and the Gen2-MI-F1B metric will identify a GUPRI as defined by FAIRsharing (see support links in this record for more information). FM Gen2-MI-F1A is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier to be provided and evaluates its identifier schema as a GUPRI. An example implementation would be to use regex matching against registered FAIRsharing identifier schemata and check the global uniqueness, persistence and resolvability fields (see support links in this record for more information). More than one match might signify an issue with the identifier schema matching. If using this example implementation, check the existing identifier schemata in FAIRsharing and please register any that you might need. The uniqueness of an identifier is a necessary condition to unambiguously refer that resource, and that resource alone. Otherwise, an identifier shared by multiple resources will confound efforts to describe that resource, or to use the identifier to retrieve it. For an in-depth understanding of the issues around identifiers, please see http://dx.plos.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>🔗 For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.NHCOKK.</p> <p>🔗 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b7f1ab.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-F2: data are described with rich metadata

F2 is concerned with the discovery of a resource of interest through, for example, search or filtering. Digital resources must be described with rich metadata – including descriptors of the content of the resource referred to by that identifier. It is hard to generally define the minimally required “richness” of this metadata, except that the more generous and comprehensive it is, both for humans and computers, the more specifically findable (in a meaningful way) it becomes in refined searches. While other principles specify metadata elements that must be present to support, for example, specific aspects of reusability (e.g. citation and license), principle F2 is primarily about discovery - that a digital resource that is well-described can be easily discovered even when the resource is unknown to the agent performing the search. Thus, this principle encourages data providers and domain experts to consider the various facets of search that might be employed by a user of their data, and to support those users in their discovery of the resource. To enable both global and local search engines to locate a resource, generic and domain-specific descriptors should be provided, that can be exposed to indexing by the relevant search facilities. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed in <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98>.

The metrics relating to this principle are **generic** and are implemented in two parts, via two metrics (see the next two sections).

The two **generic** metrics separately deal with the identified metadata being 1) structured (F2A, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2dUpZs>), and 2) grounded (F2B, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.lXAOu2>).

Use the next two card sets to either state your community’s alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition and/or optional adoption of F2A and F2B.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Structured Metadata

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle in the context of **structured metadata**. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator – Structured Metadata - Gen2-MI-F2A</p> <p><i>This metric measures whether the metadata of the record contains "structured" elements primarily for the purposes of discoverability; F2 is concerned with metadata for the purposes of discovery, while other principles (in the "Rs") that require rich structured metadata are more concerned with elements as pertains to e.g., reusability. Gen2-MI-F2A is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a GUPRI or other type of metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of any structured data. The structured elements may be in the form of hash-like content (e.g., micrograph, JSON) or in one of the various forms of linked data (e.g., JSON-LD, RDFa). Structured data is inherently easier for machines to accurately process and interpret. Even loosely-structured metadata can have reliable parsers built to consume it, including those of major search engines. Thus, it improves the findability of the record.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2dUpZs.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p><i>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</i></p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

Metadata Conforms to CESSDA DDI Codebook Profile - FM-M-CDCP

Specialised metric name and definition	<p>Metadata Conforms to CESSDA DDI Codebook Profile - FM-M-CDCP</p> <p>The Metadata Conforms to CESSDA DDI Codebook Profile metric checks if the mandatory elements of a CESSDA DDI Codebook Profile are present in the metadata and if the metadata is valid DDI. The FM-M-CDCP metric expects a metadata identifier as input.</p> <p>Using valid DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) metadata is crucial for CESSDA and social science research because it ensures discoverability, interoperability, and reusability of data across different archives and countries. By providing a standardised way to describe data, DDI metadata allows researchers to find and understand data across borders, prevents information loss, and supports the principles of FAIR data management. The CESSDA DDI profiles make clear which elements and attributes are mandatory, recommended and optional for each version of DDI that can be ingested to the CESSDA Data Catalogue.</p>								
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7610 								
Guidance	<p>Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="250 874 2078 1082"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="250 874 1003 922">URI</th> <th data-bbox="1016 874 2078 922">Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="250 922 1003 1002">https://cmv.cessda.eu/api/oas3</td> <td data-bbox="1016 922 2078 1002">CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV) API documentation: Information about CMV API</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="250 1002 1003 1082">https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html</td> <td data-bbox="1016 1002 2078 1082">CDC DDI Profiles: Information about mandatory DDI elements and attributes</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	https://cmv.cessda.eu/api/oas3	CESSDA Metadata Validator (CMV) API documentation: Information about CMV API	https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI Profiles: Information about mandatory DDI elements and attributes
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https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI Profiles: Information about mandatory DDI elements and attributes								
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	<p>Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="250 1123 2119 1329"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="250 1123 412 1171">Status</th> <th data-bbox="412 1123 1809 1171">URI(s)</th> <th data-bbox="1809 1123 2119 1329">Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="250 1171 412 1329"></td> <td data-bbox="412 1171 1809 1329"></td> <td data-bbox="1809 1171 2119 1329"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example			
Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example							

		[(reason why it is a good example)]”
Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=baa7efc7d05d55b2327beb2e2c5687c1ebf944f1ea95433f61dea267f890e847	All entries in the CESSDA Data Catalogue Aggregator are checked at time of ingestion for compliance with the relevant DDI Profile.
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=1d59715550aa2d0434ff296176dd810ad55097d40eeefe2cccec0c25c6d64bf5	Example of a dataset which is not CESSDA valid and therefore does not exist in CESSDA Data Catalogue Aggregator even if it is shown in CESSDA Data Catalogue
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure	No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle in the context of **grounded metadata**. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Grounded Metadata - Gen2-MI-F2B</p> <p><i>This metric measures whether the metadata of the record contains "structured" elements that are "grounded" in shared vocabularies primarily for the purposes of discoverability; F2 is concerned with metadata for the purposes of discovery, while other principles (in the "Rs") that require rich metadata are more concerned with elements as pertains to e.g., reusability. Gen2-MI-F2B is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a GUPRI or other type of metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of any grounded data. To be grounded, the structured elements should be represented as some type of linked data (e.g., JSON-LD, RDFa). While similar to FM Gen2-MI-F2A, this metric requires the data be in a graph format (specifically, grounded in shared vocabularies) rather than structured only (as with FM Gen2-MI-F2A). Otherwise, the intent and methodology described by this and FM Gen2-MI-F2A are the same. Structured and grounded data is inherently easier for machines to accurately process and interpret. Thus, it improves the findability of the record.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>🔗 For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IXAOU2.</p> <p>🔗 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.e05e98.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes

F3 is concerned with the identification of described resource within metadata when that metadata is separated from the actual resource it describes. The F3 principle states that any description of a digital resource must contain clearly and explicitly the identifier of that resource being described. This is especially important where the resource and its metadata are stored independently, but are nonetheless persistently linked. Descriptors should explicitly state which resources it describes; but even more than this, digital objects may have structures that disallow the addition of new fields, including fields that could point to the metadata about that resource. Therefore, sometimes the only consistent way for both humans and machines to discover the metadata of a resource is through a search for the identifier of that resource. Although implementation of each principle is up to each community, a note about the GO-FAIR Foundation's interpretation of this principle: that when FAIR principle F3 mentions that the identifier of the object should be explicitly and clearly included in the object's metadata, the GO-FAIR Foundation's interpretation assumes "explicit" refers to the mere presence of the resource's identifier in the content of the metadata record while "clear" refers to having this identifier directly and unambiguously related to the metadata record by means of a known predicate. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed in <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.820324>.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.820324>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**.

Use the next card set to either state your community's alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use of GUIDs in metadata - Gen2-MI-F3</p> <p><i>This metric measures whether the metadata document contains both its own GUID (which may be different from its address), and whether it also explicitly contains the GUID for the data resource it describes. Gen2-MI-F3 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and will check if the metadata explicitly contains the identifier for the digital resource it describes. This is generally present in the form of a qualified reference, e.g. some manner of "about" relationship, to distinguish this identifier from the numerous others that will be present in the metadata. The discovery of the digital object should be possible from its metadata. Because many digital objects cannot be arbitrarily extended to include references to their metadata, in many cases the only means to discover the metadata related to a digital object will be to search based on the GUID of the digital object itself. The Metadata GUID is used to harvest metadata, which is then tested for the data identifier. If a match is found in any test implementing this metric, the test passes. Note that there are cases where the ambiguity around whether an identifier refers to the metadata document, or to the data it describes, is determined by the interpretation of the specification being used (e.g. identifiers in DCAT are always about the data being described, and there is no identifier for the metadata itself).</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5Xy1dJ.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.820324.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-F4: (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

F4 states that digital resources must be registered or indexed in a searchable resource (e.g., a search engine). The searchable resource provides the infrastructure by which a metadata record (made accessible with a GUPRI, see principle F1) can be discovered, using either the attributes in that metadata (F2) or via the identifier of the resource itself (F3). (Text modified from: see reference URL.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**.

Use the next card set to either state your community's alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata indexed in a searchable resource

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata indexed in a searchable resource - Gen2-MI-F4</p> <p><i>This metric measures the degree to which the digital resource can be found using web-based search engines. FM Gen2-MI-F4 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates it to determine if that identifier (or one of its synonyms) can be found via a search engine using the structured content of the metadata as search terms. Most people use a search engine to initiate a search for a particular digital resource of interest. If the resource or its metadata are not indexed by web search engines, then this would substantially diminish an individual’s ability to find and reuse it. An example of an implementation that would test for a “pass” of this metric would be: the GUID provided should first resolve to its metadata (i.e. a document), then the content of that document is captured and used in a search. The results of that search are compared to the GUID of the metadata document to determine successful discovery.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p> For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-A1: (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

A1 asserts that there should be no additional barrier to the retrieval of the record by a computational agent when its access protocol (A1.1 & A1.2) results in permitted access to that record. For fully programmatic access, this requires that the identifier (F1) follows a globally-accepted schema that is tied to a standardized, high-level communication protocol. If human agents are involved, it is still necessary that the identifier (F1) be sufficient as a way of unambiguously indicating, to this non-automated agent, the record that is being requested. The “standardized communication protocol” is critical, as it provides a predictable way for an agent to access a resource, regardless of whether the access to the content of the resource is open or restricted, and regardless of whether that access is automated or aided by human action (e.g., send your request for access by email or telephone). (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7014eb>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7014eb>.

 The metrics relating to this principle are **generic** and are implemented via sub-principles (see the next two sections).

This principle is split into two distinct sub-principles, which require that the protocol being used to retrieve the (meta)data 1) is openly specified, thus making them open, free and universally implementable (A1.1, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>), and 2) clearly states the procedures for access, including authentication/authorisation where required (A1.2, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>). As such, the **generic metrics** in use for A1 are also split between these sub-principles.

Use the next two card sets to either state your community’s alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition for A1.1 and A1.2.

FAIR-A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

A1.1 states that the protocol (mechanism) by which a digital resource is accessed (e.g. queried) should not pose any bottleneck. It describes an access process, hence does not directly pertain to restrictions that apply to using the resource. The protocols underlying the World-Wide Web, such as HTTP, are an archetype for an open, free, and universally implementable protocol. Such protocols reduce the cost of gaining access to digital resources, because they are well defined and open and allow any individual to create their own standards-compliant implementation. That the access to the protocols specifications is free ensures that those lacking monetary means can equitably access the specifications and can implement them without occurring in any monetary obligations. That it is universally implementable ensures that the technology is available to all (and not restricted, for instance, by country or a sub-community), thus encompassing both the 'gratis' and 'libre' meaning of 'free'. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>.

 The metric relating to this principle is **generic**. This is the first of two sub-principles of A1.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Open protocol for (meta)data retrieval - Gen2-MI-A1.1 <i>This metric measures if the resolution protocol is universally implementable with an open protocol; protocols that are closed source or that have royalties associated with them could prevent users from being able to obtain the resource. Gen2-MI-A1.1 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and checks if the resolution protocol used is universally implementable with an open protocol. Implementations may, for example query the resolution protocol against a list of known open protocols to determine if it meets the requirements of FAIRness.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p> For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p><i>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary

A1.2 is one of the differentiators between FAIR and open data, and that aligning with the FAIR principles does not require openness, but rather that the procedure for access is clearly described. Some digital resources, such as data that have access restrictions based on ethical, legal or contractual constraints, require additional conditions/steps to be accessed. This principle is concerned with evaluation of the requester to confirm identity (authentication), that the requester's profile and credentials match the access conditions of the resource (authorization), and that the intended use matches permitted use cases (e.g. for a particular purpose only) (see also R1.1, where there are requirements to provide explicit documentation about who may use the data, and for what purposes). At the level of technical implementation, an additional authentication and authorization procedure must be specified, if it is not already defined by the protocol (see A1.1). A requester can be a human or a machine agent. In the latter case it is probably a proxy for a human or an organization to which the authentication and authorization protocol should be applied, in which case, the machine should be expected to present the appropriate credentials. The principle requires that a FAIR resource must provide such a protocol, but the protocol itself is not further specified. Although particular implementations of FAIR are up to each community, the GO-FAIR Foundation states that in practice, an Internet of FAIR Data and Services cannot function without implementing Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, which includes AAI for machines and should thus be Ontology-based and machine actionable. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>.

 The metric relating to this principle is **generic**. This is the second of two sub-principles of A1.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

Generic metric name and definition	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Protocol supports authentication/authorization - Gen2-MI-A1.2.</p> <p><i>This metric measures if the resolution protocol supports authentication and authorization for access to restricted content. Gen2-MI-A1.2 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and measures if the resolution protocol is evaluated to support authentication and authorisation. Implementations may e.g., ask the FAIRsharing registry about the data access conditions for the repository storing the digital object, or test if a link using the Dublin Core "accessRights" property is present in the metadata.</i></p>
Links to more information on the generic metric	<p> For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027.</p>
Define the alignment of your community with this metric	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

Differences from the Generic Metric

Description of differences from the generic metric	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses CESSDA Access Rights Vocabulary – FM_Gen2-MI-A1.2_M_CARV This</p> <p>metric checks whether the data access terms in the metadata belong to the controlled vocabulary called CESSDA Access Rights. The FM_Gen2-MI-A1.2_M_ARV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object for data access term usage from the CESSDA Access Rights Controlled Vocabulary.</p>
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Related resources	Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7578 		
Guidance	Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):		
	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs		
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/conditions.html	DDI 2.5 conditions specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>conditions</i> element in DDI metadata	
https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>conditions</i> element in CESSDA		
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=77e45bb5c68712689b19fe881264baea534a81a55e0ae6e1277edf2cd2f46b50	DDI <i>conditions</i> element including text “open”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=37d56897bd4890895550a6a5f465d86beeeeb864538f0655e1cf5e92d9c7d2aa	DDI <i>conditions</i> element including text “restricted”
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=34db9e3ac0368bc3c299339aeb9b64529292100b72f85d9f49b93838f7f899c	DDI <i>conditions</i> element present but does not include text

			“open” or “restricted” even if information available in CDC.
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=22301ef69ecbb0b151ba9cee90b588517e32ae2960dfb39b0519215a9bbcb40a		No <i>conditions</i> element present in DDI metadata
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues		OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure		No <i>codeBook</i> element found in OAI-PMH response
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete		Vocabulary API returns empty <i>concepts</i> array

FAIR-A2: metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

A2 focuses on keeping relevant digital resources available in the future. Data may no longer be accessible either by design (e.g. a defined lifespan within limited financial resources or legal requirements to destroy sensitive data) or by accident. However, given that those data may have been used and are referenced by others, it is important that consumers (including machines) have, at the very least, access to high quality and machine actionable metadata that describes those resources sufficiently to minimally understand their nature and their provenance, even when the relevant data are no longer available. This principle relies heavily on the “second purpose” of principle F3 (the metadata record contains the identifier of the data), because in the case where the data record is no longer available, there must be a clear and precise way of discovering its historical metadata

record. This aspect of accessibility is further elaborated in the Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f>.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0c0d21>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**.

Use the next card set to either state your community's alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata persistence - Gen2-MI-A2</p> <p><i>This metric checks if there is a policy for metadata persistence. Gen2-MI-A2 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of a persistencePolicy key. Cross-references to data from third-party’s FAIR data and metadata will naturally degrade over time, and become “stale links”. In such cases, it is important for FAIR providers to continue to provide descriptors of what the data was to assist in the continued interpretation of those third-party data. As per FAIR Principle F3, metadata must remain discoverable, even in the absence of the data (and missing data will still be explicit referenced via the data IRI within the metadata). Here are two examples of ways in which this metric might be evaluated. While a test implementation could explore the harvested metadata for something resembling a “persistence policy” property (e.g. http://www.w3.org/2000/10/swap/pim/doc#persistencePolicy), this is often unsuccessful as databases don't always include database-level persistence information at the level of a dataset. To solve this issue, test implementations can use an optional additional argument containing the URL/DOI of the FAIRsharing database record where the digital object is stored, and the FAIRsharing record metadata can be checked for the existence of a persistence policy of the database (see support links for more information). Note that for both methods of checking persistence, the presence of a persistence/preservation policy does not guarantee the quality of that policy; the linked policy may simply state that no preservation will occur.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.IEZbPK.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7c4d7f.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p><i>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/>—This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/>—This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

I1 is concerned with achieving a “common understanding” of digital resources through a globally understood “language” for machines, with an emphasis on “knowledge” and “knowledge representation”. This becomes critical when many differently formatted resources need to be visited or combined across organizations and countries and is especially challenging for interdisciplinary studies or for meta-analyses, where results from independent organizations, pertaining to the same topic, must be combined. In this context, the principle says that producers of digital resources are required to use a language (i.e., a representation of data/knowledge) that has a defined mechanism for mechanized interpretation – a machine-readable “grammar” – where, for example, the difference between an entity, as well as any relevant relationship between entities, is defined in the structure of the language itself. This allows machines to consume the information with at least a basic “understanding” of its content. It is a step towards a common understanding of digital resources by machines, which is a prerequisite for a functional Internet of FAIR Data and Services. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648>.

 The metrics relating to this principle are **generic**.

There is a choice of two **generic** metrics that implement this principle. Each community should choose either the *soft* (with a looser interpretation of FAIR I1) or *strict* (with a more precise definition of FAIR I1) version of the metric depending on their needs. As such, the **generic** metrics in use for I1 are either the *soft* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.qUroF6>) or the *strict* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.l8fVBn>). You should pick one of the next two card sets, and will not need both.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft)

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (soft) - Gen2-MI-I1A</p> <p><i>This metric measures the use of a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. Gen2-MI-I1A is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points for any hash-style metadata (e.g., JSON or microformat) or Linked Data. The unambiguous communication of knowledge and meaning (what symbols are, and how they relate to one another) necessitates the use of languages that are capable of representing these concepts in a machine-readable manner. There is debate in the community about what languages would be considered "knowledge representation languages", as such this Maturity Indicator is broken into two sub-MIs (Gen2-FM-I1A and Gen2-FM-I1B). This metric (Gen2-FM-I1A) takes a loose definition, such that any kind of structured information is sufficient.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p> For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR; I will either use the strict metric, or this entire principle is not applicable for our needs.</p>

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict)

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Use a Knowledge Representation Language (strict) - Gen2-MI-I1B</p> <p><i>This metric measures the use of a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. Gen2-MI-I1B is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points for Linked Data. The unambiguous communication of knowledge and meaning (what symbols are, and how they relate to one another) necessitates the use of languages that are capable of representing these concepts in a machine-readable manner. There is debate in the community about what languages would be considered "knowledge representation languages", as such this Maturity Indicator is broken into two sub-MIs (Gen2-FM-I1A and Gen2-FM-I1B). This MI (Gen2-FM-I1B) takes a strict interpretation, accepting only formats that are ontologically grounded and machine resolvable.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.l8fVBn.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ec5648.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR; I will either use the soft metric, or this entire principle is not applicable for our needs.</p>

FAIR-I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

I2 uses “vocabularies” as the methods for unambiguous representation of concepts that exist in a given domain. The use of shared, and formally structured (principle I1), sets of terms is an essential part of FAIR. Terminology systems, including flat “vocabularies”, hierarchical “thesauri” and more granular specifications of knowledge such as data models and consistently structured ontologies, play an important role in community standards. However, the vocabularies used for metadata or data also need to be FAIR in their own right so that users (including machines) can fully understand the meaning of the terms used in the metadata. I2 requires that the vocabulary terms used in the knowledge representation language (principle I1) can be sufficiently distinguished, by a machine, to resolve to the intended defined meaning and thus ensure detection and prevention of “false agreements” as well as “false disagreements” on exact meaning of the identifier. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af>.)

The metrics relating to this principle are **generic**.

For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af>.

There is a choice of two **generic** metrics that implement this principle. Each community should choose one or both the *loose* (with a looser interpretation of FAIR I2 that just checks the vocabulary terms resolve) or *strict* (with a more precise definition of FAIR I2 where the terms resolve to linked data) version of the metric depending on their needs. As such, the **generic** metrics in use for I2 are either the *loose* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.E3Nr1d>) or the *strict* version (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.RCUuvt>). You should choose one or both of the next two card sets.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (loose)

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (loose) - Gen2-MI-I2A <i>The FAIR Maturity Indicator Gen2-MI-I2A measures if the (meta)data uses vocabularies that are, themselves, FAIR. For interoperability, it must be possible to identify data that can be integrated like-with-like. This requires that the data, and the provenance descriptors of the data, should (where reasonable) use vocabularies and terminologies that are, themselves, FAIR. In this loose MI, the test is only if the vocabulary terms resolve (e.g. to a human-readable page). It does not test if the terms resolve to machine-readable information. A second Maturity Indicator (Gen2-FM-I2B) is for that stricter test. A valid result is the successful resolution of a proportion of predicates in Linked Data. This metric is relevant to all types of digital objects.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>🔗 For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.E3Nr1d. 🔗 For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p><i>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</i></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs. <input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section. <input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR; this entire principle is not applicable for our needs.</p>

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (strict)

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (strict) - Gen2-MI-I2B</p> <p><i>The FAIR Maturity Indicator Gen2-MI-I2B measures if the (meta)data uses vocabularies that are, themselves, FAIR. It is not possible to unambiguously interpret metadata represented as simple keywords or other non-qualified symbols. For interoperability, it must be possible to identify data that can be integrated like-with-like. This requires that the data, and the provenance descriptors of the data, should (where reasonable) use vocabularies and terminologies that are, themselves, FAIR. In this strict Maturity Indicator, we test if the vocabulary terms resolve to machine-readable linked data. A second Maturity Indicator (Gen2-FM-I2A) is looser than this MI. A valid result is the successful resolution of a proportion of predicates in Linked Data to more linked data. This metric is relevant to all types of digital objects.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↗ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.RCUuvt.</p> <p>↗ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR; this entire principle is not applicable for our needs.</p>

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (strict)

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Metric - FAIR Maturity Indicator - Uses FAIR Vocabularies (strict) - Gen2-MI-I2B</p> <p><i>The FAIR Maturity Indicator Gen2-MI-I2B measures if the (meta)data uses vocabularies that are, themselves, FAIR. It is not possible to unambiguously interpret metadata represented as simple keywords or other non-qualified symbols. For interoperability, it must be possible to identify data that can be integrated like-with-like. This requires that the data, and the provenance descriptors of the data, should (where reasonable) use vocabularies and terminologies that are, themselves, FAIR. In this strict Maturity Indicator, we test if the vocabulary terms resolve to machine-readable linked data. A second Maturity Indicator (Gen2-FM-I2A) is looser than this MI. A valid result is the successful resolution of a proportion of predicates in Linked Data to more linked data. This metric is relevant to all types of digital objects.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.RCUuvt.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.96d4af.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not applicable to our definition of FAIR; we will a) use our specialised metric and optionally the loose generic metric; or b) this entire principle is not applicable for our needs.</p>

FAIR-I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

I3 is concerned with the placement of (meta)data within the broader context of the research data ecosystem; knowledge representing a resource is connected to that of other resources to create a meaningfully interlinked network of data and services. A “qualified reference” is a reference to

another resource (i.e., referencing that external resource's persistent identifier), in which the nature of the relationship is also clearly specified. For instance, when multiple versions of a metadata file are available, it may be useful to provide links to prior or next versions using a named relation such as “prior version” or “next version” (using an appropriate community standard relationship that itself conforms to the FAIR principles). This principle therefore also relates to the good practice to clearly distinguish between metadata (files/containers) and the resources they describe. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ae22b8>.)

For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ae22b8>.

The metric relating to this principle is **generic**.

Use the next card set to either state your community’s alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Qualified outward links - Gen2-MI-I3</p> <p><i>This metric measures whether the linked data metadata contain links that are not from the same source (domain/host). Gen2-MI-I3 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to check for links to external sources. Data silos thwart interoperability. Thus, we should reasonably expect that some of the references/relations point outwards to other resources, owned by third parties; this is one of the requirements for 5 star linked data. The URI representation of the record's GUID is examined for its domain name. Any Linked Data that can be found after resolution of the GUID is parsed to determine the hostname of the object-resources. This Metric could be created in a quantitative form if the user/community wished for tests implementing it to be very strict, counting the number of externally-pointing links.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.LLXjWx.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ae22b8.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-R1: (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

R1 focuses on enabling machines and humans to assess if the discovered resource is appropriate for intended reuse, given a specific task. This is in contrast to F2, which at first glance seems similar, however F2 is concerned with enabling effective attribute-based search and query (findability) instead of metadata for reusability. The term “plurality” is used to indicate that the metadata author should be as generous as possible, not narrowly presuming who the secondary consumers might be, and therefore provide as much metadata as possible to support the widest variety of use-cases and agent needs. The sub-principles R1.1, R1.2 and R1.3 further define some critical types of attributes that contribute to R1. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.821487>.)

 For more information on the top-level principle R1, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.821487>.

Metric R1.1 is **generic**.

 Metrics R1.2 and R1.3 are **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metrics for R1.2 and 1.3 in ways appropriate to their needs.

This principle is split into three distinct sub-principles, which require that the (meta)data 1) is released with a clear usage licence (R1.1, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7612c1>), 2) are linked to detailed provenance (R1.2, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>), and 3) meet relevant domain-specific community standards (R1.3, <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8e0027>). As such, the **generic metrics** in use for R1 are also split between these sub-principles.

Use the next R1.1 card set to either state your community’s alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition. Use the R1.2 and R1.3 card sets to create specialised metrics for those sub-principles.

FAIR-R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

R1.1 states that digital resources and their metadata must always, without exception, include a license that describes under which conditions the resource can be used, even if that is “unconditional”. By default, resources cannot be legally used without this clarity. The absence of a license does not indicate “open”, but rather creates legal uncertainty that will deter (in fact, in many cases legally prevent) reuse. Note also that the combination of resources with permissive as well as more restrictive license conditions may lead to adverse effects, and ultimately preclude the use of the combined resources for particular purposes. In order to facilitate reuse, the license chosen should be as open as possible. While the implementation of a FAIR principle is up to each community, note the following addition comments from the GO-FAIR Foundation: 1) if a license that cannot be found by an agent, is effectively the same as no license at all, 2) beware of licenses that may be different for a data resource and the metadata that describes it, which has implications for the indexing of metadata v.v. findability, 3) this principle also reiterates the need to separate and permalink data and metadata. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.aff99f>.)

 For more information on this principle, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.aff99f>.

Metric R1.1 is **generic**. (Remember that the metrics for next two sub-principles are **specialised**.)

Use the next card set to either state your community’s alignment with the existing generic metrics, or to create your own specialised definition.

FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata contains link to license

This card provides information on the **generic metric** for this principle. Read it carefully and then tick the appropriate box to define the alignment of your community with this metric. If the generic metric does not match your community requirements, then follow the instructions after the card to specify how your requirements differ from the generic metric description.

<p>Generic metric name and definition</p>	<p>FAIR Maturity Indicator - Metadata contains link to license - Gen2-MI-R1.1</p> <p><i>This metric checks for information regarding the data licence information. Gen2-MI-R1.1 is a domain- and object-type agnostic metric that expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of a licence key. Optionally, if Gen2-MI-R1.1 is also provided with the FAIRsharing database URL or DOI associated with the database in which the metadata is stored, then the test will instead look for the existence of a nonzero value in the licence field(s) marked as applicable to the database content (see support links for more information). Example implementations of this metric could include an optional argument providing the FAIRsharing URL/DOI for the database in which the metadata is stored; in this case, the FAIRsharing record's licence field(s) would be queried. If there is a nonzero value in the licence field(s) marked as 'applicable to content', and the URL(s) resolves to something, then the test will pass. If there is no optional FAIRsharing URL/DOI, an implementation could check the metadata for the presence of a "License" key, or of one of a set list of predicates exists, and has a resolvable URL as its value. Note that for both methods of checking licences, the presence of a licence does not guarantee the quality of that licence; however, FAIRsharing licences will link to SPDX where available.</i></p>
<p>Links to more information on the generic metric</p>	<p>↑ For more information on this generic metric, including documentation and justifications, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.YAdSwh.</p> <p>↑ For more information on the principle linked to this generic metric, including documentation and justifications for the implementation of this principle, please see https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.aff99f.</p>
<p>Define the alignment of your community with this metric</p>	<p>Tick the box to cross out the incorrect statement(s).</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is sufficient for our needs.</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> This generic metric is not sufficient for our needs, and we will describe the differences in the next section.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> This principle and related metrics are not applicable to our definition of FAIR.</p>

FAIR-R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

R1.2 is concerned with information such as how the resource was generated, why it was generated, by whom, under what conditions, using what starting-data or source-resource, using what funding/resources, who owns the data, who should be given credit, and any filters or cleansing processes that have been applied post-generation. Provenance information helps people and machines assess whether a resource meets their criteria for their intended reuse, and what data manipulation procedures may be necessary in order to reuse it appropriately. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3e9860>.)

💡 This metric is **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metric in a way appropriate to their needs. (Remember that the metric for R1.1 was **generic**, and the metric for next sub-principle – R1.3 - is also **specialised**.)

Use the next card set to create your own specialised definition.

📄 For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3e9860>.

Metadata Contains CESSDA Provenance Information

Specialised metric name and definition	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Contains CESSDA Provenance Information - FM_R1-2_M_CPI</p> <p>This metric checks if certain elements containing provenance information (Creator, Funder and Publisher) appear in the metadata. The FM_R1-2_M_CPI metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of certain DDI elements and attributes.</p> <p>The provenance information is important for two main reasons: 1) give credit to the persons / organisations that contributed or funded the dataset and 2) enable to track connections between other research products (e.g. find the datasets /literature funded by the same funder or authored by the same creator or published by the same publisher).</p>										
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7571 										
Guidance	<p>Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="255 831 2134 1278"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="255 831 1346 874">URI</th> <th data-bbox="1352 831 2134 874">Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 879 1346 954">https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/AuthEnty.html</td> <td data-bbox="1352 879 2134 954">DDI 2.5 AuthEnty specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>AuthEnty</i> element in DDI metadata</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 959 1346 1066">https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/grantNo.html</td> <td data-bbox="1352 959 2134 1066">DDI 2.5 grantNo/@agency specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>grantNo/@agency</i> attribute in DDI metadata</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 1070 1346 1150">https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/distrbtr.html</td> <td data-bbox="1352 1070 2134 1150">DDI 2.5 distrbtr specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>distrbtr</i> element in DDI metadata</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 1155 1346 1278">https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html</td> <td data-bbox="1352 1155 2134 1278">CESSDA DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>AuthEnty</i> (Creator) / <i>distrbtr</i> (Publisher) elements / <i>grantNo/@agency</i> (Funder) attribute in CESSDA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/AuthEnty.html	DDI 2.5 AuthEnty specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>AuthEnty</i> element in DDI metadata	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/grantNo.html	DDI 2.5 grantNo/@agency specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>grantNo/@agency</i> attribute in DDI metadata	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/distrbtr.html	DDI 2.5 distrbtr specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>distrbtr</i> element in DDI metadata	https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CESSDA DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>AuthEnty</i> (Creator) / <i>distrbtr</i> (Publisher) elements / <i>grantNo/@agency</i> (Funder) attribute in CESSDA
URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI										
https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/AuthEnty.html	DDI 2.5 AuthEnty specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>AuthEnty</i> element in DDI metadata										
https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/grantNo.html	DDI 2.5 grantNo/@agency specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>grantNo/@agency</i> attribute in DDI metadata										
https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/distrbtr.html	DDI 2.5 distrbtr specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>distrbtr</i> element in DDI metadata										
https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CESSDA DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>AuthEnty</i> (Creator) / <i>distrbtr</i> (Publisher) elements / <i>grantNo/@agency</i> (Funder) attribute in CESSDA										
Positive, Negative	<p>Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.</p>										

and Indeterminate Examples	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=0fee2172edb9fe5062b8d862737491e41ce232765af65f26c587a3d528f1eda0	One or more of creator, funder and publisher information present
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=28fdb1cd2ba626e16673e9962d158eaa0abd9709a14d8667108a179e72d7212f	One or more of creator and publisher information but no funder present
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=9ae0439593c38e7f272d0cf93839e3961f686ff38f8b051f3c470e1f041f7128	One or more publisher information and no funder and no creator present
	Negative	N/A	No publisher, creator or funder information present
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing

	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure	No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

FAIR-R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

R1.3 states that where community standards or best practices for data archiving and sharing exist, they should be followed. Disciplinary communities often create minimal information standards, reporting guidelines, required terminologies and more. These reporting guidelines and minimal information standards will often describe the minimal set of metadata items required to assess the quality of the data acquisition and processing and to facilitate reproducibility. Note that providing truly rich and reusable metadata often requires richer metadata than these standards might provide. For a list of such standards, FAIRsharing (this registry) can be consulted. (Text modified from: see reference URL as listed at <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.87d197>.)

💡 This metric is **specialised**. This means that we expect communities to create their own metric in a way appropriate to their needs. (Remember that the metric for R1.1 was **generic**, and the metric for the previous sub-principle – R1.2 - is also **specialised**.)

Use the next card set to create your own specialised definition.

📄 For more information on the principle that this metric must implement, including documentation and justifications its implementation, please see <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.87d197>.

Metadata uses CESSDA ELSST Keywords

Specialised metric name and definition	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses CESSDA ELSST Keywords – FM_I2_M_CEK</p> <p>The metric checks whether keywords used in the metadata belong to the ELSST controlled vocabulary. The FM_I2_M_CEK metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object for standardised keyword usage from CESSDA ELSST.</p>										
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7577 										
Guidance	<p>Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="255 708 2132 1070"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="255 708 1335 751">URI</th> <th data-bbox="1341 708 2132 751">Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 756 1335 831">https://github.com/cessda/cessda.skg-if-openapi.elsst.server/blob/main/README.md</td> <td data-bbox="1341 756 2132 831">ELSST keyword API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 836 1335 951">https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/keyword.html</td> <td data-bbox="1341 836 2132 951">DDI 2.5 keyword specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>keyword</i> element and its <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> attributes in DDI metadata</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 956 1335 1070">https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html</td> <td data-bbox="1341 956 2132 1070">CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>keyword</i> element and its attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	https://github.com/cessda/cessda.skg-if-openapi.elsst.server/blob/main/README.md	ELSST keyword API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/keyword.html	DDI 2.5 keyword specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>keyword</i> element and its <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> attributes in DDI metadata	https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>keyword</i> element and its attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA
URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI										
https://github.com/cessda/cessda.skg-if-openapi.elsst.server/blob/main/README.md	ELSST keyword API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels										
https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/keyword.html	DDI 2.5 keyword specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>keyword</i> element and its <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> attributes in DDI metadata										
https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>keyword</i> element and its attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA										
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	<p>Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="255 1110 2132 1318"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="255 1110 412 1153">Status</th> <th data-bbox="418 1110 1809 1153">URI(s)</th> <th data-bbox="1816 1110 2132 1318">Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="255 1158 412 1318"></td> <td data-bbox="418 1158 1809 1318"></td> <td data-bbox="1816 1158 2132 1318"></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example					
Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example									

		[(reason why it is a good example)]”
Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=c23e8a47f7562ec9abf32f0ad53c1da0e6c563d0e2b36f10279746c91348ddcf	One or more keywords present that explicitly declares ELSST via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND have a <i>vocabURI</i> that points to <i>elsst.CESSDA.eu</i> AND the <i>keyword text</i> matches a value retrieved via the ELSST keyword API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=e2bfcff447c5ddc6c93c29836a4a8965fa30cbf867e90f854a3352871848f93e	No keywords present that explicitly declare ELSST via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND don't have a <i>vocabURI</i> that points to <i>elsst.CESSDA.eu</i>
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=b36ee86b5530f0eaa5efdd8e2e4536ff92f9259433b20f8fac3d725e519e748c	Keywords present that don't declare ELSST via <i>vocab</i> attribute BUT have a <i>vocabURI</i> that points to <i>elsst.CESSDA.eu</i>

	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=5f6b80769ee8e1e56d4aa05149c8f2299b6afa1939f2b0ca8c5b30ca02b7cbae	Keywords present that explicitly declare ELSST via <i>vocab</i> attribute BUT don't have a <i>vocabURI</i> that points to <i>elsst.CESSDA.eu</i> AND the <i>keyword text</i> does not match a value retrieved via the ELSST keyword API
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=adbb73ac20ac969efb221e5b7e823165c81422ce17f62f59a48747153121fb84	Keywords present that explicitly declare ELSST via <i>vocab</i> attribute but don't have a <i>vocabURI</i> attribute
	Indeterminate	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=024a089a0091aa5f0e53f61d3a4c5549d009d3179875ec5496fad1d304541c77	Instead of terms there are only some identifiers
	Indeterminate	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=979b3171b4dc0f4dfd87084bbfe62c608d035942e1330f2505523a78008fb748	No language code available for ELSST keyword API validation
	Indeterminate	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=44044130e4660692ef6014b29fc08ed4b0179caaf909eb793488f54d2a402325	CESSDA catalogue URL without keyword elements

	Indeterminate	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=1bf9e812d15ea729196121c1f81fef3a5107e7bac4694a51dfd88fb2b1124b55	OAI-PMH identifier maps to no known item
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

Metadata Uses CESSDA Topic Vocabulary

Description of differences from the generic metric	FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses CESSDA Topic Vocabulary - FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_CTV	
	This metric checks whether metadata topics belong to the controlled vocabulary called CESSDA Topic Classification. The FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_CTV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object for standardised topic usage from the CESSDA Topic Classification Controlled Vocabulary.	
Related resources	Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7576 	
Guidance	Guidance links <i>(at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance)</i> :	
	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI
	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/v2/api-docs	CESSDA Topic Classification Vocabulary API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels

	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/TopicClassification?lang=en	CESSDA Topic Classification Vocabulary: Information how to use vocabulary
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/topcClas.html	DDI 2.5 topcClas specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>topcClas</i> element and its attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in DDI metadata
	https://cmv.CESSDA.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>keyword</i> element and its attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.	
	Status	URI(s)
Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=b514a801fbc76f843e9791c268d40d3ab373dfc197303871b4cfa18179923ed5	One or more topic present that explicitly declares CESSDA Topic Classification via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND have a <i>vocabURI</i> that includes <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> AND the <i>topcClas</i> text matches a

		value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA Topic Classification API
Positive	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=dbbc2fc17c99ab877daa072f7cc6280da068cde57589fd0b3ef241f44574e13b	One or more topic present that explicitly declares CESSDA Topic Classification via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND don't have a <i>vocabURI</i> that includes <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> AND the <i>topcClassText</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA Topic Classification API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=e32e28bb3fe8496bf870928f393db5ab55936b33f4ce93f3edad9047058197d0	One or more topic present that explicit declares CESSDA Topic Classification via <i>vocab</i> attribute but do not have a <i>vocabURI</i> that includes

		<i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> AND the <i>topcClass text</i> do not match a value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA Topic Classification API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=10a12eafb8f986e78a970de5d9409a8efb18b31cc5a43c72db09369a1727a82b	One or more topic present but no declaration of CESSDA Topic Classification via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> AND the <i>topcClass text</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA Topic Classification API)
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=810ef1d547f924eaa5c10825a5621342d11eeea5a731a339990a6b66ab5dbd01	One or more topics present that explicitly declares CESSDA Topic

			<p>Classification via vocab attribute AND have a <i>vocabURI</i> that includes <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> but the <i>topcClass</i> text does not match a value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA Topic Classification API</p>
	Negative	<p>https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=5f6b80769ee8e1e56d4aa05149c8f2299b6afa1939f2b0ca8c5b30ca02b7cbae</p>	<p>One or more topic present but no declaration of CESSDA Topic Classification via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>TopicClassification</i> AND the <i>topcClass</i> text does not match a value retrieved via the CVS CESSDA</p>

			Topic Classification API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=86d2f2b4b4d012e71660c62dc4c941281516b74170d670e251eaff841ba49e41		No <i>topcClass</i> present in DDI metadata
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues		OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure		No <i>codeBook</i> element found in OAI-PMH response
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete		Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

Metadata Uses DDI Mode Of Collection Vocabulary

Description of differences from the generic metric	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Mode Of Collection Vocabulary - FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DMOCV</p> <p>This metric checks if certain information elements contain terms from the DDI Mode of Collection controlled vocabulary. The FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DMOCV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of terms from the specified controlled vocabulary.</p>
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7574

Guidance	Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):		
	URI		Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs		Mode of Collection Vocabulary API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/ModeOfCollection?lang=en		DDI Mode of Collection Vocabulary: Information how to use vocabulary
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/collMode.html		DDI 2.5 collMode specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>collMode</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in DDI metadata
https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html		CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>collMode (Data collection mode)</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA	
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=6990c361d92fb69e46e1f267d0c63e8a48d8647f30b782400f97a31b2dc745c9	Mode of Collection term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i>	

			including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>collMode</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=39d0d6dae8c00fa33e046235788d0b582fce572ff82a4f2e24aca345d99f2251		Mode of Collection term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> not including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>collMode</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=363f9b7398e7fec7d401b0acbfd60aabac76301750588b36eed27fc36dc681d		Mode of Collection term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the

		<i>collMode</i> does not match a value retrieved via the CVS API)
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=8075de0509649c69849199e186775595d013f47c8208ac6dd6fd3040f845d9e	Mode of Collection term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>collMode</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=fb7c8f4b5703ac727e0b38b341d07fbd40f39a2f0b303270a14e0042eac7b8cc	Mode of Collection term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>collMode</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API

	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=4c70d55197e2c80afe593f8463e4edc4ee441e70c356a64dba20208758291394	Mode of Collection term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> but in the wrong place in metadata AND the <i>collMode</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API if incorrect “a” tag is removed
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=efc3d8686e0a9f74340e88d5ee7f5af4676451d37dbca7fb3dfe851370515934	No Mode of Collection term(s) present
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure	No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response

	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array
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Metadata Uses DDI Analysis Unit Vocabulary

Description of differences from the generic metric	FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Analysis Unit Vocabulary FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DAUV This metric checks if certain information elements contain terms from the DDI Analysis Unit controlled vocabulary. The FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DAUV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of terms from the specified controlled vocabulary.		
Related resources	Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7575 		
Guidance	Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):		
	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs	DDI Analysis Unit Vocabulary API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels	
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/AnalysisUnit?lang=en	DDI Analysis Unit: Information how to use vocabulary	
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/onlyUnit.html	DDI 2.5 onlyUnit specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>onlyUnit</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in DDI metadata	
	https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html	CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>onlyUnit (Analysis Unit)</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA	

Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=6990c361d92fb69e46e1f267d0c63e8a48d8647f30b782400f97a31b2dc745c9	Analysis Unit term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>onlyUnit</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=39d0d6dae8c00fa33e046235788d0b582fce572ff82a4f2e24aca345d99f2251	Analysis Unit term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via <i>vocab</i> attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> not including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary</i>	

			<i>name</i> AND the <i>anyUnit</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=363f9b7398e7fec7d401b0acbdf60aabac76301750588b36eed27fc36dc681d		Analysis Unit term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>anyUnit</i> does not match a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=18075de0509649c69849199e186775595d013f47c8208ac6dd6fd3040f845d9e		Analysis Unit term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>anyUnit</i> matches a

		value retrieved via the CVS API)
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=fb7c8f4b5703ac727e0b38b341d07fbd40f39a2f0b303270a14e0042eac7b8cc	Analysis Unit term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>anlyUnit</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=4c70d55197e2c80afe593f8463e4edc4ee441e70c356a64dba20208758291394	Analysis Unit term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> but in the wrong place in metadata AND the <i>anlyUnit</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API if

			incorrect “a” tag is removed
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=efc3d8686e0a9f74340e88d5ee7f5af4676451d37dbca7fb3dfe851370515934		No Analysis Unit term(s) present
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues		OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure		No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response
Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete		Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array

Metadata Uses DDI Time Method Vocabulary

Description of differences from the generic metric	<p>FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Time Method Vocabulary - FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DTMV</p> <p>This metric checks if certain information elements contain terms from the DDI Time Method controlled vocabulary. The FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DTMV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of terms from the specified controlled vocabulary.</p>
Related resources	<p>Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://fairsharing.org/7573

Guidance	Guidance links (at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance):		
	URI		Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/v2/api-docs		Time Method Vocabulary API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels
	https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/vocabulary/TimeMethod?lang=en		DDI Time Method: Information how to use vocabulary
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/timeMeth.html		DDI 2.5 timeMeth specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>timeMeth</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in DDI metadata
tps://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html		CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>timeMeth (Time Dimension)</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA	
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=6990c361d92fb69e46e1f267d0c63e8a48d8647f30b782400f97a31b2dc745c9	Time Method term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including	

			<i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>timeMeth</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=39d0d6dae8c00fa33e046235788d0b582fce572ff82a4f2e24aca345d99f2251		Time Method term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> not including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>timeMeth</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=363f9b7398e7fec7d401b0acbdfd60aabac76301750588b36eed27fc36dc681d		Time Method term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>timeMeth</i> does not

			match a value retrieved via the CVS API
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=18075de0509649c69849199e186775595d013f47c8208ac6dd6fd3040f845d9e		Time Method term(s) present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no vocabURI including vocabularies.CESSDA.eu and vocabulary name AND the timeMeth matches a value retrieved via the CVS API)
Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=fb7c8f4b5703ac727e0b38b341d07fbd40f39a2f0b303270a14e0042eac7b8cc		Time Method term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no vocabURI including vocabularies.CESSDA.eu and vocabulary name AND the timeMeth matches a value retrieved via the CVS API)

	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=4c70d55197e2c80afe593f8463e4edc4ee441e70c356a64dba20208758291394	Time Method term(s) present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> but in the wrong place in metadata AND the <i>timeMeth</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API if incorrect “a” tag is removed)
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=efc3d8686e0a9f74340e88d5ee7f5af4676451d37dbca7fb3dfe851370515934	No Time Method term(s) present
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure	No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response

	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array
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Metadata Uses DDI Sampling Procedure Vocabulary

Description of differences from the generic metric	FAIR Metric - Metadata Uses DDI Sampling Procedure Vocabulary - FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DSPV This metric checks if certain information elements contain terms from the specified controlled vocabularies. The FM_Gen2-MI-I2A_M_DSPV metric expects a metadata identifier and evaluates the digital object that identifier points to for the presence of any the following controlled vocabularies.		
Related resources	Your definition of FAIR for this principle relates to the following standards, databases and/or policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://fairsharing.org/7572 		
Guidance	Guidance links (<i>at whatever level of granularity you prefer. It might be general information about the type of identifier your community requires, or information about FAIR in your community, or more specific test guidance</i>):		
	URI	Descriptive guidance text associated with the URI	
	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/v2/api-docs	DDI Sampling Procedure API documentation: Information about querying and retrieving controlled vocabulary labels	
	https://vocabularies.CESSDA.eu/vocabulary/ModeOfCollection?lang=en	DDI Sampling Procedure Vocabulary: Information how to use vocabulary	
	https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Codebook/2.5/xmlschema/schemas/codebook_xsd/elements/sampProc.html	DDI 2.5 sampProc specification: Technical guidance on proper use of <i>sampProc</i> element and its child element <i>concept</i> with attributes <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in DDI metadata	

	https://cmv.cessda.eu/documentation/profiles.html		CDC DDI 2.5 profiles: Guidance on the use of the <i>sampProc</i> (Sampling Procedure) element and its child element <i>concept</i> with <i>vocab</i> and <i>vocabURI</i> in CESSDA
Positive, Negative and Indeterminate Examples	Indicative or exhaustive examples of digital objects within your community that pass or fail the metric or return an indeterminate response.		
	Status	URI(s)	Description(s); one per URI e.g., “Indicative positive negative indeterminate example ([reason why it is a good example])”
	Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=fcdf8ad65e3650b4e3e8e5c379cdaaa67ee93b90addeb20616e9188c30e78db9	One or more Sampling Procedure terms present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>sampProc</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
Positive	https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=1fd1d946e3172439fb913af07952b08d06e5a59be26e07f4b9a565f847b27cd5	One or more Analysis Unit, Time Method and Mode	

			<p>of Collection present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> not including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>sampProc</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API</p>
	Negative	<p>https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=420a818da4cbe9b2a78c3e02226c34d27b182676dbd68f7cd62b4802ef8ef88b</p>	<p>One or more Sampling Procedure terms present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.cessda.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> AND the <i>sampProc</i> does not match a value retrieved via the CVS API</p>

	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=f1241bb4e2062634b0ec3a41947c3c87cae62834646200d344f3033a6bc328a3	<p>One or more Sampling Procedure terms present with declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no vocabURI including vocabularies.CESSDA.eu and vocabulary name AND the sampProc matches a value retrieved via the CVS API)</p>
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=e3ac1c6f84edcbe34673df6615181bb723661e76341d139fe3d4124d3187fd86	<p>One or more Sampling Procedure terms present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND no vocabURI including vocabularies.CESSDA.eu and vocabulary name AND the sampProc matches a value retrieved via the CVS API</p>

	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=c47e871942a33b25a7d66d3dc1a1ce04cfdcf7f5f2420c0bf6ea65ce06e6762b	One or more Sampling Procedure terms present but no declaration of vocabulary name via vocab attribute AND <i>vocabURI</i> including <i>vocabularies.CESSDA.eu</i> and <i>vocabulary name</i> but in the wrong place in metadata AND the <i>sampProc</i> matches a value retrieved via the CVS API
	Negative	https://datacatalogue.CESSDA.eu/oai-pmh/v0/oai?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=oai_ddi25&identifier=c90c5d0eb27fb88356ffef20abc02143bdd52a09cf0206af3e8efb9ac5f0ad4b	No Sampling Procedure terms present
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL causing connectivity issues	OAI-PMH endpoint timeout or HTTP error during metadata fetch when testing
	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL with incomplete DDI structure	No codeBook element found in OAI-PMH response

	Indeterminate	Any CESSDA catalogue URL when vocabulary structure is incomplete	Vocabulary API returns empty concepts array
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